

SURVEILLANCE CARD Q-Fever- Environmental sampling in high-risk areas

	Characteristics	Description
1	Surveillance component name	Environmental sampling for <i>Coxiella burnetii</i> in high-risk areas.
2	Surveillance aim	Early detection of an increase in human health risk, i.e., early epidemic detection.
3	Target species and group	Goats and sheep, adult primiparous and multiparous females.
4	Target sector / production type	Breeding farms.
5	Geographical area covered	Areas which: - were identified as high prevalence areas (e.g., identified by the surveillance activity "Indicator-based surveillance of abortions in ruminants"). have a relevant density of susceptible livestock in close proximity to human settlements or recreational areas .
6	Age group	Not applicable.
7	Sampling point and strategy	Environmental samples collected on (and in the vicinity of) goat and sheep farms.
8	Sampling time period	Lambing / kidding season (if weather conditions allow airborne distribution of pathogen).
9	Sampling matrix	According to a recent review (1), the most commonly tested sample type was dust which also yielded the highest bacterial loads of $>10^8$ bacteria/cloth. The MD8 (Sartorius) air sampler was used widely for air sampling. Soil was the only sample type for which a validated laboratory protocol was established specifically for <i>C. burnetii</i> .
10	Type of disease indicators	Bacterium.
11	Sampling unit	Geographic area.
12	Allocation of animal groups /animals to sampling	Not applicable.

13	Testing protocol / Diagnostic test	DNA purification from sample according to standardized protocol followed by quantitative PCR testing.
14	Design prevalence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
15	Level of confidence (only relevant for probability-based sampling)	Not applicable; biased (non-random or non-representative) sample of the population.
16	Contribution of the component to the surveillance system	Since the transmission to humans is mostly via the contaminated environment, environmental testing is an important component for the early detection of the risk areas.
17	Other pathogens that could be targeted with this surveillance component	Not applicable.
18	References	<p>1) Abeykoon, A. M. H., Clark, N. J., Soares Magalhaes, R. J., Vincent, G. A., Stevenson, M. A., Firestone, S. M., & Wiethoelter, A. K., 2021. <i>Coxiella burnetii</i> in the environment: A systematic review and critical appraisal of sampling methods. <i>Zoonoses and public health</i>, 68(3), 165–181. https://doi.org/10.1111/zph.12791</p> <p>2) Kersh GJ, Wolfe TM, Fitzpatrick KA, Candee AJ, Oliver LD, Patterson NE, Self JS, Priestley RA, Loftis AD, Massung RF., 2010. Presence of <i>Coxiella burnetii</i> DNA in the environment of the United States, 2006 to 2008. <i>Appl Environ Microbiol</i>. 2010 Jul;76(13):4469-75. doi: 10.1128/AEM.00042-10. Epub 2010 May 14. PMID: 20472727; PMCID: PMC2897457.</p> <p>3) Bielawska-Drozd, A., Cieřlik, P., Mirski, T., Gawel, J., Michalski, A., Niemcewicz, M., ... & Kocik, J., 2014. Prevalence of <i>Coxiella burnetii</i> in environmental samples collected from cattle farms in Eastern and Central Poland (2011–2012). <i>Veterinary microbiology</i>, 174(3-4), 600-606.</p>
19	Additional comments	In a study in the US, prevalence in environmental samples ranged from 6-44% (2), A study in Poland found <i>C. burnetii</i> DNA in 4.5% of samples.

